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Abstract

A history of corporate governance (CG) research demonstrates that it has been essentially devoted to Anglo-Saxon large corporations. Thus, the study of CG systems was conducted within a particular national institutional context of formal rules and informal rules. It, therefore, led to the promotion of mechanisms such as the board of directors as well as managers' markets and takeovers. The opposition between the disciplinary and cognitive functions of governance that support the presentation of the different micro theories, could also, in the continuum, identify the analysis of national systems of corporate governance (NSCG). This dichotomy would result, in the presentation of disciplinary analysis of the NSCG that presume that the essential influencing factor of efficiency – often measured according to the productive perspective by the growth of the national economy – is based on the protection of the interest of the different contributors of production factors, with precedence given, under the influence of the shareholder view, to financial investors. [4]

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The analysis supporting the disciplinary perspective based upon the appropriation of organizational rents and the protection of the financial investor's rights are of financial origin. They begin with the hypothesis that the financial system plays a central role in explaining economic growth and prosperity. The influence of the system in relation to information and transaction costs is exercised through five functions:

- Risk management: the facilitation of the trading, hedging, diversification, and pooling of the risk;
- Allocation of resources;
- The monitoring of managers and control of corporations;
- The mobilization of savings; and
- The facilitation of the exchange of goods and services. [4, p.17]

Within a financial perspective, efficiency depends on the protection of the financial investor's rights against attempts at expropriation by the managers and dominating shareholders. When contrasting the US corporate government system with the European Union one it essential to outline that in all the Member States under consideration, there are significant legal controls on the activities of the directors and managers, which are intended to ensure that officers act within their powers, and conduct their business efficiently. Such controls vary in detail and in the sanctions provided for in case of the breach. [2, p.18]

One aspect of the consideration of the role of corporate governance is that the ownership structures of European and US companies even historically is very difficult. The primary difference is that the European companies in general do not display the same diversity of share ownership as US companies do. But, surely, there are more other differences among them. [4, p.20]

Discussions relating to the corporate law in the United States are discussed very often, but are rarely understood. Mainly the reason for is that it is not regarded as a part of the federal law and, therefore, to say that there is any concrete government agency to enforce it actively, is not so. In general, corporations can be formed when one or more investors transfer their assets

into a specific separate account (i.e. the corporation) and, therefore, in exchange the investors are granted a divisible common interest (i.e. shares) on that account. The consequence of those two concurrent operations is the "separation" of share ownership from both corporate ownership and corporate control of those assets. Surely, corporate law contains certain provisions that regulate corporate constitutions as well. Those particular provisions aim to deal with corporation's preparations for the exercise of control as well as monitoring over the corporation's accounts, i.e. arrangements for putting forward and into effect specific decisions concerning the disposition of all corporate assets. [4, p.20] Corporate directors, who are the shareholders' elected representatives, delegate authority to corporate officers the obligation to manage corporate affairs in the ordinary course of business. At any rate, there are included also some provisions that touch personal liabilities of directors and officers for actions committed in their corporation's name and for its account. [2, p.21] Basically, corporate directors as well as officers can become personally liable in case of failing to perform their duties with "due care" and "loyalty" on behalf of the corporation. [4, p.71]

Under the corporate law, the control of corporations by shareholders is limited simply with the election of directors and auditors – often nominated by the Chief-executive officers (CEOs), and relying on the following provision of corporate law, directors, typically limit their role with selecting CEOs and after with supervising their performance and productivity. The only additional element to shareholders' and directors' control is that they make decisions on matters outside the scope of the ordinary course of business of the corporation, i.e. changes that may occur in terms of the corporation's operating business, mergers, acquisitions, divestments as well as the payment of dividends. In respect of those kinds of situations, shareholders and directors, basically, make their decisions relying upon the proposals or professional suggestions initiated by their CEOs. In any event, neither shareholders nor directors in the United States have any authority to take

any measures in the corporation's dealings with third parties. All these types of activities are actualized by the CEOs. More to this point, no one but only they can sign documents and generally act in the corporation's name. In other words, they are deemed to be like "legal representatives" of the corporation. Notwithstanding, it is to be noted that the CEOs may delegate to other corporate officers the power to make and also actualize certain decisions. [4, p.75]

Corporate officers have an obligation to report to their corporation's directors and shareholders' representatives. This duty is based upon the concept of separation of corporate ownership and corporate control. "While corporations might incur liability to individuals and other corporations under the law of general obligation or contract law for their CEOs to act in their corporations' names and for their accounts, CEOs do not incur any liability to other individuals or corporations in terms of three those acts." [2, p.30] At long last, the CEOs and other officers can be considered lawfully responsible by the United States government and even subject to criminal sanctions in case they break a government regulation when carrying out their obligations on behalf of organization. More clearly stated, corporate officers are subject to two types of performance standards, generally called as "fiduciary duties" which are, the "duty of care" and the "duty of loyalty". [4, p.75]

By receiving the appointment, every single officer is bound to the "duty of loyalty" in all commitments he undertakes on behalf of corporations: i.e. the officers will avoid "conflicts-of-interest" between their corporations' interests and their own ones. It is of high importance to act upon this duty because in case the tort to that occurs, depending on the essence of the consequences, the officer may be subject up to criminal sanctions.

By accepting the appointment, they are bound also to "duty of care" the application of which to officers' decisions is subject to the "*business judgment*" rule. Accordingly, courts apply the duty of care on the basis of the facts that are reasonably open to officers at the time that they are making and/or implementing their decisions, but not on such basis of facts as that the officers could not have known, even if they had been showing conscientiousness. [2, p.30]

It is to be outlined the fact that directors also are subject to demonstrate the same performance of standards that are applicable to officers. In other words, directors, as well have to apply the "duty of care" and "duty of loyalty" when perform their obligations in corporation. Notwithstanding, there is an essential difference. The applied standards to corporate officers are "professional" standards in contrast to those applicable to directors which are lower, "unprofessional" ones. By restating this thesis, corporate officers are obliged to demonstrate the care and loyalty of corporate officers, while directors are expected to demonstrate ones of a reasonable person. [4, p.81]

Various models got from the European legislation that accommodate employee stakeholder-ship are portrayed here, as the Proprietorial Interest Model, the Management – Labor Consultative Model, which will

incorporate within its rubric a consideration of worker participation on boards of directors, and finally the Trade Union model building on existing trade union structures and consequently regulation thereof. [6]

One of the fundamental provisions in this set of rights is the protection which is given to employees from dismissal without cause. Additionally, certain grounds for dismissal will be outlawed completely. Thus the employer will have to present some reasons for dismissals and basically, go through a standard set of warning procedures before dismissal occurs in the first instance. All EU member states have this type of legislation as part of their employment law. More essentially, in the context of concerns that CG writers express, particularly in the United States, about accountability of management regarding decisions to close plants, European labor legislation also protects the worker in redundancy situations by mandating certain payments and certain consultative procedures. In comparison with the US, its "employment-at-will" doctrine has evolved from a strong commitment to the contractual concepts of equal bargaining power and freedom of contract. It has been maintained in many states, due to the strong arguments made in favor of this approach, particularly in the academic sector [9]. Additionally, it has been argued when the state intervene in such matters, distorts and weaken the dynamics of private bargaining. More to the point, it has been debated that the employees have the capacity to protect themselves through bargaining and that there will be a tradeoff between such states mandated rights and other benefits. [6, p.20-21]

Germany

The most essential feature of the German ownership system, which has equivalents elsewhere, most notably in Japan, is the role of the banking sector. Particularly, the role of institutional investors is limited if compared with the role incurred by banks that exercise a dominant influence disproportionate to their actual ownership. The background for this dominance is based upon the fact that German banks are the beneficiaries of a kind of "proxy system" whereby shareholders delegate voting to the bank through which their brokerage business is conducted. Also the voting system and process in Germany has entire differences from what exists in "Anglo-American" model. In Germany there is no proxy system whereby management exercises the shareholders' voting power, and they vote their own shares or shares are voted by institutions, basically banks, as "custodians" for their shares. [2, p.28-29]

In Germany, all corporations as well as limited liability companies employing over fifty employees are operated by the two tier-board system. Employees, in their turn, are represented on the supervisory board; the number of labor representatives depends on, specifically, the number of employees. The management board of the two-tier system is appointed usually for a five-year term and is controlled in terms of ability to dismiss by the supervisory board. However, the management can only be dismissed prematurely for cause. This is viewed as being one factor in the unpopularity of hostile takeovers as a form of management control. Secondly, the meetings of shareholders have a distinct

role in the large German corporation in contrast to the Anglo-American models. [2, p.28-29] The power of shareholders' meeting is limited to decisions regarding approval of accounts, distribution of half of the annual balance sheet profits, election of half the members of the supervisory board and decisions concerning specific structural changes. [4, p.81]

"The powers of management in a German private company are divided between the manager and the general meeting, in accordance with the provisions of the *GmbH Gesetz*, and the articles of the company. When a private company has a few members who are also managers, the shareholders may be able to take decisions falling within the powers of the managers and the general meeting whenever they meet." [3, p. 265]

The double board system has long been an essential feature of German law relating to the public company. The main meaning is that the management board is entrusted with the function for managing the company, whilst the supervisory board has a controlling task. Members of the management board are appointed by the supervisory board for renewable periods that do not exceed five years term. The essential role of the supervisory board also includes the preparation of annual financial statements. [3, p.269]

France

In France [10, p.7] the basic Company Law Code in operation at present was enacted in 1966. French Company Law allows for a one or two-tier management board. Labor representation is mandated for state enterprises but not for private enterprises. If a *Societe Anonyme* employs more than fifty a "works council" must be established whose members are elected exactly by the employees. Afterwards, the works council is entitled to send two of its members to meetings of either the management or supervisory board as non-voting observers. Notwithstanding, it is ordinary for companies with works councils to have preliminary board meetings without the representatives of the works council. This inherent challenge in co-determination arising from essential differences between employee and management constituencies has been recognized as a difficulty with employee representation. [2, p.29]

A French SARL is managed by managers put under the control of shareholders. The managers must be natural persons but not members of the company or French citizens. It is to be noted that the first managers are appointed by the articles, and then, all subsequent appointments are made by resolutions passed by the members in general meeting. The managers may act on behalf of the company in all circumstances, but must not do such acts that the law reserves to the members, or which are contrary to the company's articles outside the scope of managing the business which it carries on. [3, p.269]

The members' power to dismiss managers is one of high importance, because no more than six months after the end of the fiscal year they have to approve the company's accounts, which consist of the manager's reports, inventories of assets, balance sheet. The managers need to send to each of shareholders no less than fifteen days prior to the annual general meeting a duplicate of the company's trading account, profit and loss

account, balance sheet and managers' report for the proceeding financial year, together with the report of auditor on the accounts and any group accounts, as well as the text resolutions to be proposed at the meeting.

"Directors, managing directors, and the executive officers of public companies adopting the traditional single board system as well as members of the executive supervisory boards of such companies employing the double board system are subject to a number of statutory controls which have features in common. The purpose of the strict rules that govern agreements between such persons and their company is to avoid a conflict between the personal interests of the persons concerned and their duties to the company." [3, p.270]

In case where the company has a traditional structure, and the agreement is with the managing director, one of the directors, or executive officers, or the holder of shares carrying more than ten per cent of the voting rights, it must receive the prior approval of the board of directors before execution. If it is directly between a member of the supervisory or executive board and the company, or between a person possessing more than ten percent of the voting rights and the company, before execution there the general meeting must approve it. The same situation is where such persons are indirectly interested in a contract with the company.

Position of shareholders: The shareholders in general meeting are treated as being the supreme body of the company. However, shareholders' meeting may not usurp the powers belonging to the chairman or executive board. The annual meeting falls within the former category, as does a meeting called to pass an ordinary resolution. [2, p.31] Shareholders may act either individually or collectively, and thus they may exercise specific rights. Particularly, individual shareholders have rights to obtain access to particular documents in case it is necessary. Shareholders that hold five percent or more of the company's capital and shareholders' association, also have rights in terms of submit questions to the chairman of the board of the directors or the executive board about one or more management transaction. [3, p.272]

United Kingdom

It is now recognized generally that although there is no question of the total approximation or harmonization of the company law of the Member States, a considerable body of European Company Law has been brought into existence. [1]

The division of powers between the general meeting and the board is in principle a matter for the articles. The position may be contrasted that in the United States and many other European countries, where certain functions are treated as managerial ones, must be entrusted to the board. [1] Fiduciary duties are owed to British companies by the directors which are not much closely paralleled in other European jurisdictions, apart from the Republic of Ireland. It is accepted that the interests of the company include those of present and future shareholders and when the companies are insolvent or on the brink of the insolvency, the interests of the creditors. "If directors use the power conferred by the articles for a purpose other than that for which it was conferred, their conduct may be impugned, and they

may not avail themselves of the defense that they honestly believed that what they did was in the interests of the company. The present rule is applicable even when the directors derive no profit from the transaction, and believe themselves to be acting bona fide in the interests of the company.” [3]

One important corporate control is placed on directors and shadow directors. Directors or shadow directors may be liable for fraudulent and/or wrongful trading. [12] It makes such persons personally liable to contribute to the assets of a company which has gone into indirect liquidation if at some time before the commencement of the liquidation, they knew or ought to have concluded that there was no responsible prospect that the company would avoid going into insolvent liquidation. [1, p.109]

Directors also incur liability if they are responsible for negligently managing corporate affairs. The earlier decision on the required standard of care and skilled tended to impose a subjective criterion based upon the degree of care and skill they might be expected of a person of the director’s knowledge and experience. However, an objective standard of care and skill is now required of directors employed under a service contract. The same is true of non-executive directors, who do not have such a contract. [3, p.268]

The formal rules about holding general meetings often prove to be ignored in the case of the private companies, and the stipulations of section 336 of the Act which provide that there should be annual general meeting in public companies, do not apply to private companies. In principle, if the directors are responsible for the breach of duty, the general meeting has to decide whether to take actions against them, and a minority shareholder cannot normally bring an action on the company’s behalf if the members in general meeting choose not to do so.

“Vote-less” shares may be less common than they formerly were in the United Kingdom: shares may, nonetheless, have various voting rights attached to them, and shareholders’ voting and other agreements are commonplace in private and joint companies. In private companies, the directors often hold the majority of shares, and the general meeting, may prove to be an ineffective control over their activities, this may be the case in certain public companies as well. [2]

Conclusion

The European companies in general do not display the same diversity of share ownership as US companies do. However, this is not true for the United Kingdom and to a lesser extent, Ireland, where companies which are quoted on the London or Dublin stock exchange display characteristics similar to US quoted companies in terms of ownership. Interestingly these countries share a common law heritage with the US. Overall, the public equity markets are not in general the primary source of capital for many Europeans companies. In Europe a trend towards privatization has added to the “phenomenal growth” of equity markets in a number of OECD countries in Europe. This has been further fueled by “a growing process of disintermediation in the financial markets, shifting savings from the banking sector to equity (and bond) markets.” [7] On the other hand, growth

in institutional shareholding has probably led to a decrease in diversity of share ownership in the US, with latest figures showing that “less than 100 large non-bank financial institutions hold approximately 20% of the top 20 more liquid markets in the world. Despite evidence of convergence, it must be emphasized however, that figures for stock exchange turnover show a marked difference between the level of stock exchange activity in Europe overall (32,500m Euro for 1998) and the US (13bn Euro for 1998).” [8]

Three hypotheses are presented here. Firstly, it is now accepted that the various ownership structure of continental European companies compared with the ownership structure of US companies, determines how monitoring of management takes place. “If to accept the capital markets theory of management accountability, which is put forward in relation to US companies, it is clear that in view of the fact that European companies are not the subject to the same sort of activity on the equity markets this theory will not readily apply in the European context. Thus these markets could not be described as a forum in which management performance could be assessed. Similarly, most European companies do not operate in a market which allows or indeed permits an active take-over culture of the sort which dominated US corporate culture, particularly in the 1980s.” [2, p.108]

A second hypothesis is that various types of ownership structures have had a significant impact on the acceptability of including other constituencies as stakeholders. The argument is that ownership structures of European companies have facilitated a more tightly controlled method of CG system, that permits, for instance, close monitoring by creditors as stakeholders. This, in turn, has allowed for a more open acceptance of some level of monitoring by other stakeholders such as employees.

And finally, it is debated that the more tightly or closely held ownership of European companies has, in a political sense, facilitated a corporate culture which is more open to the influence of centralized planning by government authorities, whether this is at national level or at EU level. [2, p.110] Present governance structures in European companies have a significant impact on the acceptability of the type of planning evidenced by EU policy documents.

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